

A Research Paper on Pradhan Mantri Matru Vandana Yojana' (PMMVY)

Prof. Vinayak R Gramopadhye

Assistant Professor, Vasantiaodada Patil
Institute of Management Studies and
Research, Sangli, Maharashtra, India

Prof. Milind M Samudre

Assistant Professor, Vasantiaodada Patil
Institute of Management Studies and
Research, Sangli, Maharashtra, India

I. INTRODUCTION

Under-nutrition adversely affects majority of women in India. Every third woman is undernourished and every second woman is anemic. An undernourished mother almost certainly gives birth to a low birth weight baby. When poor nutrition starts in-utero, it extends throughout the life cycle since the changes are largely irreparable. Due to economic and social sufferings, many women continue to work to earn a living for their family right up to the last days of their pregnancy. Furthermore, they resume working soon after childbirth, even though their bodies might not be capable of doing the task, thus preventing their bodies from fully recovering on one hand, and also obstructing their ability to exclusively breastfeed their young infant in the first six months. The Maternity Benefit Programme has been implemented from 1st January 2017 in all the districts of India in accordance with the provision of the National Food Security Act, 2013. The programme is named as 'Pradhan MantriMatruVandanaYojana' (PMMVY). The present paper provides an insight of the PMMVY.

II. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To know the Objectives of Pradhan MantriMatruVandanaYojana
- To understand the facilities offered by Pradhan MantriMatruVandanaYojana

III. METHODOLOGY

The data and information for the study is gathered from secondary sources like magazines, newspapers,

various websites including website of Pradhan MantriMatruVandanaYojana.

IV. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

- Time limitations faced while collecting the secondary data
- All the data cannot be generalized.

V. Pradhan MantriMatruVandanaYojana

Pradhan MantriMatritvaVandanaYojana (PMMVY), previously known as the Indira Gandhi MatritvaSahyogYojana (IGMSY), is a maternity benefit program run by the government of India. Pradhan MantriMatruVandanaYojana (PMMVY) is a Maternity Benefit Programme that is implemented in all the districts of the country in accordance with the provision of the National Food Security Act, 2013.

VI. Key Objectives of Pradhan MantriMatruVandanaYojana

1. Providing partial compensation for the wage loss in terms of cash incentive s so that the woman can take adequate rest before and after delivery of the first living child.
2. The cash incentive provided would lead to improved health seeking behaviour amongst the Pregnant Women and Lactating Mothers (PW& LM).

VII. Target beneficiaries

1. All Pregnant Women and Lactating Mothers, excluding PW&LM who are in regular

employment with the Central Government or the State Governments or PSUs or those who are in receipt of similar benefits under any law for the time being in force.

2. All eligible Pregnant Women and Lactating Mothers who have their pregnancy on or after 01.01.2017 for first child in family.
3. The date and stage of pregnancy for a beneficiary would be counted with respect to her LMP date as mentioned in the MCP card.
4. Case of Miscarriage/Still Birth :
 - A beneficiary is eligible to receive benefits under the scheme only once.
 - In case of miscarriage/still birth, the beneficiary would be eligible to claim the remaining instalment(s) in event of any future pregnancy.
 - Thus, after receiving the 1st installment, if the beneficiary has a miscarriage, she would only be eligible for receiving 2nd and 3rd installment in event of future pregnancy subject to fulfillment of eligibility criterion and conditionalities of the scheme. Similarly, if the beneficiary has a miscarriage or still birth after receiving 1st and 2nd instalments, she would only be eligible for receiving 3rd instalment in event of future pregnancy subject to fulfilment of eligibility criterion and conditionalities of the scheme.
5. Case of Infant Mortality: A beneficiary is eligible to receive benefits under the scheme only once. That is, in case of infant mortality, she will not be eligible for claiming benefits under the scheme, if she has already received all the instalments of the maternity benefit under PMMVY earlier.
6. Pregnant and Lactating AWWs/ AWHs/ ASHA may also avail the benefits under the PMMVY subject to fulfilment of scheme conditionalities.

VIII. Benefits under PMMVY

- Cash incentive of Rs 5000 in three instalments i.e. first instalment of Rs 1000/- on early registration of pregnancy at the Anganwadi Centre (AWC) / approved Health facility as may be identified by the respective administering State / UT, second instalment of Rs 2000/- after six months of pregnancy on receiving at least one ante-natal check-up (ANC) and third instalment of Rs 2000/- after child birth is registered and the child has received the first cycle of BCG, OPV, DPT and Hepatitis - B, or its equivalent/ substitute.

- The eligible beneficiaries would receive the incentive given under the Janani Suraksha Yojana (JSY) for Institutional delivery and the incentive received under JSY would be accounted towards maternity benefits so that on an average a woman gets Rs 6000 / -

IX. Progress of Pradhan MantriMatruVandanaYojana

- It is a conditional cash transfer scheme for pregnant and lactating women of 19 years of age or above for first two live births.
- It provides partial wage compensation to women for wage-loss during childbirth and childcare and to provide conditions for safe delivery and good nutrition and feeding practices.
- In 2013, the scheme was brought under the National Food Security Act, 2013 to implement the provision of cash maternity benefit of ₹6,000 stated in the Act.
- It is Centrally Sponsored Scheme under which the cost sharing ratio between the Centre and the States & UTs with Legislature is 60:40, for North-Eastern States & three Himalayan States, it is 90:10 and 100% Central assistance for Union Territories without Legislature.

CONCLUSION

In fine, Pradhan MantriMatruVandanaYojana is a comprehensive economic scheme for working women. Pradhan MantriMatruVandanaYojana lays an emphasis on raising social alertness towards the significance of nutrition is essential in order to attain the preferred results.

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